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UNDERSTANDING ETHICS FROM NATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

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Ethics and Religion

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Introduction /Meaning

*"Where there is purity in the heart, there is beauty in the character,
Where there is beauty in the character there is harmony in the home,
When there is harmony in the home, there is order in the nation,
When there is order in the nation there is peace in the world."*

Bhagwan Sri Sathya Sai Baba

The dictionary meaning of ethics is accepted beliefs that control human behavior especially such a system based on morals. Ethics have also been defined as the study of what is morally right and what is wrong. The Sanskrit equivalent being neethi.

There is no consensus on the definition of religion either. However, it may be defined as a cultural system of designated behavior and practices, morals, beliefs in their founder or propagator if any, sanctified places, organizations that relates humanity to supernatural or spiritual elements.

Spirituality probably in our opinion is a better or higher connotation of the word religion, a concept which is more broadbased, liberal and universal.

The term spirituality and religion are often used interchangeably and inconsistently. For example miller and martin often used the term interchangeably even after stating that spirituality may not belong to any organized religion.¹

Ethics, Religion are topics very closely or intricately linked. The ethical instinct although not the most prominent, is the most consistent persistent factor in religious life.ⁱⁱ Ethics are somewhat difficult to define. In religious context however they can be called the principles or values or the essence on which the whole edifice of religion is based. They are in a way the conscience, soul or heart of religion. Religion is just dogmatism or fanaticism without ethics. And here lies the importance of ethics. Ethics have or can have a very wide range, parameter as far as religion is concerned. However, ethics can vary from religion to religion.

Scope of Ethics

Ethics can vary from religion to religion, individual, subjects etc. The basic framework of ethics especially in the context of Indian spirituality including Yoga as given in Patanjali Yoga Sutras comprises of Sathya- Truth, Dharma – Righteousness, Ahimsa- Non-violence, Aparigraha- Non-possesion, Asteya – Non-stealing, Shanti –Peace, Prema- Love etc.. Ethics are intricate to the whole construction or edifice of religion. Truth is not only reality or the voice of conscience or reproducing exactly whatever we see , hear , experience but the reality of life and that is life is not permanent but the soul is. Therefore, in Indian spirituality the search for truth, the search for the permanent, the realization of one’s own self has been given lot of emphasis. Again, the term Ahimsa means non-violence in word, thought, actions and deeds and not merely physical violence. In Jainism it is said Ahimsa Paramo Dharma that is Ahimsa is the biggest Dharma. At the root of Ahimsa lies the inherent principle of divinity residing in all beings and also love for entire creation, including the environment. Everything is considered a manifestation of divinity especially in the Vedic concept and hence worship of stones, trees, rivers, water, air, land etc and in it is hidden the concept of ecological preservation. Similar is the concept of love. It is important to love and serve all as all are his manifestations. . “Sathya is the current, Dharma is the wire and Shanti is the bulb. When the current flows to the bulb it burns brightly. This light is love (Prema) .You will see that Sathya , Dharma, Shanti together form the constituents for prema.”ⁱⁱⁱ Again defining love Bhagwan Sri Sathya Sai Baba

Says ,” Love in words is Truth , Love in Action is Righteousness , Love in thought is Peace, Love in Discrimination is Non-violence, Love is the undercurrent of all human values “.

In Bhagwat Gita it is said that He resides in the heart of everyone. Ramkrishna Paramhansa used to say “Service to man is service to God”. Respect for all religions including one’s own in other words mutual respect for other religions, peaceful coexistence and developing a broad perspective , a broader outlook forms subject matter of ethics. It teaches us not to be fanatic, dogmatic and blind in our religious practice. Religion is a subject matter of practice and not for expansion. Expansion is ancillary. It also requires that we respect an apparently non-religious person or an atheist. It requires we respect individual point of view, opinions, differences, customs etc. Enticing, bribing or in any way offering incentives for religious purposes are contrary to religious ethics. Indulging in violence, terrorism, circulating misinformation or feeling innocent minds or brainwashing them with false concepts of religion, using certain part in some scriptures to spread misinformation or creating a ideology based on that etc is contrary to religious ethics. Again, forced conversion, superiority complex etc in religious matter all run contrary to religious ethics. Fundamentalist ideologies, expansionist views, religious intolerance, rigid views in terms of religion or God, considering one’s own views as correct can never form subject matter of ethics. Freedom to practice religion of one’s own choice, freedom to hold one’s own religious views this are also part and parcel of religious ethics.

Religious ethics underscores the importance of discipline, self restraint, control of senses, mind, even controlling our resources, our environment, giving up sense pleasures, Brahmacharya, control of our emotions, and controlling our reactions. It teaches us that the kingdom of happiness is within ourselves and not outside or not in any individual, any object .Happiness which is derived from outside is just transient .But true happiness is to be found nowhere but inside or within. Ethics is however not mere information which is abundant in today’s age, it is wisdom which

comes from within. The source of ethics is the heart, is our inner self, is nature or universe itself. Therefore, no amount of teaching or reading will help in the development of ethics until and unless it comes from within. It has to flower from inside the recesses or cave of our heart. It is in the bosom of love that the child called ethics is really born. Ethics can exist independent of religion too because they are universal in nature however religion is a mere skeleton without ethics. So ethics is primary and religion is secondary. And all religious disputes, quarrels, fundamentalism, ideological warfare will stop once we realize this important point. Ethics have to emerge from the realization that entire creation is divine, that divinity is at the core of every individual, trees ,animals, nature etc and the establishment of ethics depends on the way we work to conserve , preserve, maintain the sacred and purity of that universal divinity.

The theory of Karma is equally important and integral part of ethics. As we reap so we sow. As is the action so is the reaction. Religion also teaches us to love for our motherland. As lord Rama said to Bharata “Janani Janma Bhumischa Swargadapi Gariyasi” .This means the physical mother and the motherland are greater than heaven itself.^{iv}

Ethics however do not simply imply morals or values or in a strict sense idealism. The Bhagwat Gita is a grand example of this. The Gita was taught in a battle field. The battle field is nothing but our life, Kauravas and Pandavas represent the forces of evil and virtue. There is a constant struggle going on between good and bad, virtue and vice, tolerance and intolerance but the path of truth, the path of righteousness should never be given up. If necessary we have to stand up, fight for the cause of righteousness. The Bhagwat Gita teaches us the importance of duty and how it should be performed. It teaches us the importance of selfless service. It gives us the concept of non-doership, we are mere instruments in His hands or higher forces of nature. We should give the sense of doership and surrender all our actions to Him which purifies, sanctifies all our actions. We must give up the six enemies called Kama(Desire), Kroddha (Anger), Lobha (Greed), Moha (Delusion) , Mada (Ego)

,Matsarya(Jealously). And cultivate six virtues Viswasam (Faith or confidence), Sahasam (Courage), Dhairayam (Patience), Buddhi (Intelligence), Sakti (Strength), Parakaram (Valour).^v It teaches us that in spirituality there may be so many different like the path of knowledge, the path of action, the path of devotion etc but all this paths lead to the same action. We can be in the world yet attain our goal, it is not essential to give up the world – it is enough if we detach ourselves from the fruit of action and surrender it to the almighty. The Bhagwat Gita reminds us that physical body is temporary but the self is permanent. The Bhagwat Gita teaches us the path of action, the zeal –the enthusiasm to fight life with energy, righteousness, devotion and firm faith in the almighty.

Research Studies on religion , Ethics, values etc

Religion and ethics are positively correlated with mental health outcomes. ^{vi}.In Canada due to multiculturalism more people are preferring to identify themselves as spiritual than religious.^{vii} There is growing body of researches, medical professionals etc who are using spirituality, ethics, religion etc to advance their practice.^{viii}

The Concept of Unity, Purity and Divinity

Unity, Purity and Divinity as advocated by Bhagwan Sri Sathya Sai Baba forms the core of spiritual or religious ethics. He says,” There is only one religion, the religion of love; there is only one God He is omnipresent, there is only one caste the caste of humanity, there is only one language the language of the heart.

Whatever divides is contrary to religious ethics and whatever unites is definitely forms subject matter of spiritual ethics. The underlying unity in diversity is at the core of Indian spirituality. Isaavasyam Idam sarvam – the lord dwells in all beings

Role of Spiritual leaders and the changing dynamics of ethics

Ethics in no way are static but extremely dynamic, flexible and often reflect or resound with changing times however the core principles or values remain the same. Spiritual leaders who descended on planet earth from time to time have greatly

influenced the dynamics of ethics. So simplification, rationalization, upgradation , reformation, upliftment, equality, equanimity, tolerance, mutual respect, removal of superstitious beliefs, removal of ignorance, use of our discriminative faculties, social equality, gender equality, cleanliness, social –environmental awareness, proper use of resources or preservation of valuable resources, preservation of ecological balance, modernizing spirituality, raising the standards of religion, introducing the or emphasizing or attaching the concept of seva, service, education to religion have been key measures undertaken by such spiritual leaders from time to time. For example:- Raja Ram Mohan Roy abolished the system of Sati, Mahapurush Srimanta Shankardev of Assam abolished inequality, superstitious beliefs etc from religion, He brought about the concept of Ek naam Dharma. Ram Krishna Paramhansa gave the concept of service to man is service to God. Swami Vivekananda highlighted the glory, greatness of Indian spirituality, Sri Sathya Sai Baba by His life teachings and service showed that religion is something much more than preaching. It is more a matter of practice, seva or service, love, devotion , education etc. He showed the way of practical spirituality which is much more than some hollow doctrine limited to words, whose effects can be perceived in their results. He taught us that spirituality is transformation of the individual, the human heart and life. He gave us the valuable concept of educare and taught us that while education is for living , educare is for life. Educare is based on the principle of love. Harmony between man and nature , man and man.^{ix} He showed us the way in which we can raise our life from animal to man and from man to divine.

Consciousness the highest form of ethics

The end is more important than the means. If ethics we assume is the means realization of self or discovery of own's own self or the cosmic connection is the end. As Swami Vivekananda has rightly said that the greatest knowledge is the knowledge of the self. In Bhagwat Gita it is said that the soul is neither born nor dies, it is eternal, all pervading, birthless, beyond time and space. It cannot be destroyed by weapons, it cannot be burnt by fire, it cannot be moistened or wetted by water and

it cannot be dried by wind. It is ageless, eternal, sanathan or the ancient one. It changes bodies like we change old clothes. The physical body is but temporary, subjected to birth and death. Sense control, the practice of Brahmacharya, the concept of religion, mind control are all means towards that end of self realization. Once that has been achieved nothing more remains to be achieved. It is like the convergence of the rivers into the seas after which the individual merges into cosmic consciousness. Ayam Athma Brahma says the atharva veda that is I am the atma. The Vedas clearly indicate that we are much more than mere flesh and blood, we are infact the highest reality. In every padartham (object in the universe) , there is a parartham(Supreme Principle), the physical object is matter. The supreme principle within it is the energy. There is no matter without energy or energy without matter. The Vedas proclaimed this by saying that the supreme is the Anoraniyan (subtlest of the subtle) and the Mahathomahiyam (vastest of the vast). On speaking about the consciousness the Kena Upanishad clearly says it is the ear of the ears, the mind of the mind, the speech of the speech, the breath of the breath and the eye of the eye. "The mind is like the moon which receives its light from the sun . It has no light of its own. It shines because of the light from the Atma. When the sun shines, the moon is hardly visible."^x. Consciousness is the crux around which the whole Vedas, Upanishads, the Bhagwat Gita and the entire Indian Spirituality has revolved, evolved and centered.

Discussion

Religion and ethics form an interesting topic of discussion. Ethics as we have wide gamut of things as far as religion is concerned. Its scope or dimension are extensive . But ethics too are a means to the final goal of self realization. The Vedas, Upanishads orient themselves towards that final goal. It has been the aim of important spiritual leaders including Swami Vivekananda, Adi Shankarcharya etc. Here we have discussed basically the common points, ethos, values forming the bridge between all religions basically. We have discussed points which are universal in nature, which can add value to our life, which can help us draw the positives from

all religion, which can add value to human life, even form part of our educational system. The belief and idol may be important but much more important than that is the practice and the ideal. In Jainism three things have been given lot of importance that is Samyak Gyana(Right Knowledge), Samyak Charitra (Right conduct), Samyak Darshan (Right vision). There can be conflict, differences as far as the traditions , cultures , customs ,system etc are concerned but there can be hardly confusion as far as the basic human values are concerned which are timeless and universal in nature.

Conclusion

Religion hardly holds any value without ethics and hence a proper study and understanding of both is required. The reason why religion in some cases has become fanatic or dogmatic is the missing link or misinterpretation or a lack of understanding or proper study or relational study, practice of both religion and ethics. So a proper grasping and practice of both religion and ethics is required for a harmonious world. This understanding of religion and ethics will help our perspective to grow, will develop our horizons, will help our wisdom or understanding or intellect to mature and in a way refined and the emergence of a universal mindset .This understanding will lead to the brotherhood of man and fatherhood of God as told by Sathya Sai Baba. Ethics as we have said forms the backbone of religion hence their proper study, appreciation, following or imbibing this principles into one's life one's behavior, attitude is required. If religion can be taught in the context of ethics it is our feeling that it will become an extremely interesting, valuable study and also a better world order. It will break narrow boundaries of hatred, intolerance, animosity, fundamentalism, terrorism, gender inequalities, castes, race, and violence. The link between ethics and religion if it can be clearly established, taught etc will greatly appreciated given its role in creating a harmonious society as a subject matter of education. Religion or the practice of religion is definitely a journey more than ethics. There are lot of debates ranging from science and spirituality, spirituality and materialism, spirituality and secularism but often this arises from a lack of

knowledge about the true essence of spirituality. The basic human values are timeless and universal. "What the world needs today is neither a new order nor a new education system nor a new religion. The remedy lies in a new mind, in a heart filled with holiness. Holiness must take root and grow in the minds and heart of people everywhere. The good and the godly must endeavor to promote this task as the one great spiritual work they have to undertake." Sri Sathya Sai Baba.^{xi}

Refernces

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^{xi} Bhagwan Sri Sathya Sai Baba, “ *Divine discourse* ” , reprinted in Sanathana Sarathi , Decemeber 1981.P 274